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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Synovial sarcoma is the fourth most commonly occurring sarcoma, accounting for 7-8% of all sarcomas (Weiss, Goldblum, & Folpe, 2007). It most frequently occurs in young adults, with up to 30% being manifested during the first two decades of life (Okcu et al., 2003). The term synovial sarcoma was coined to denominate tumors arising near tendon sheaths and joint capsules. Despite its name, synovial sarcomas do not appear to arise from synovial membranes, but from unknown multipotent stem cells that are capable of differentiating into mesenchymal and/or epithelial structures and lack synovial differentiation (Holloway et al., 2007).

Case Presentation: A 15-year-old female, gravida 1, parity 1, presented with a complaint of swelling of the right vulva of increasing discomfort for four months (Figure 1).

Figure 1

She had no other gynaecological history and reported no mass elsewhere. Clinical examination revealed a healthy woman with a well-defined deep mobile mass in the right labium majus. The patient underwent excision of the swelling under general anaesthesia and the mass (Figure 2), which did not appear to be attached to adjacent structures, was dissected free of underlying tissue.

Figure 2

Surgical margin was reported as positive in one area. Transducin-like enhancer of split 1 (TLE1), which is highly sensitive for synovial sarcoma, was found to be positive on immunohistochemistry. No evidence of systemic disease was found on the post-diagnostic PET scan. On post-operative examination of the patient, the surgical margins appeared good and no stiffness was felt at the scar line. The patient was offered the options of re-excision +/- radiotherapy or direct radiotherapy. In consultation with radiation oncology, adjuvant radiotherapy was planned for the scar line with preservation of the pelvic organs.

Conclusion: In the literature, a recurrence 1.2 years later was reported in a 33-year-old patient who was treated with a monophasic 5 cm partial radical vulvectomy and vulvoplasty and did not receive adjuvant treatment due to negative surgical margins. In another 50-year-old patient, 7 years of disease-free survival was achieved with adjuvant radiotherapy without re-excision after surgical resection with a positive surgical margin. A 26-year-old patient with biphasic morphology underwent surgical resection, had a negative surgical margin with re-excision after surgical resection, and despite receiving adjuvant radiotherapy, died in the third year of disease (Dicken et al., 2010; Kolin et al., 2020; White et al., 2008). Vulvar synovial sarcoma is a rare malignant soft tissue tumour and should be considered in patients presenting with vulvar mass.

This study does not require ethics committee approval.

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Sarcoma, synovium, vulva

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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